

A REVIEW OF ENVIRONMENT, ENERGY AND NATURAL RESOURCES LAW AND POLICY IN THE REPUBLIC OF CONGO

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(1) INTRODUCTION

The Republic of Congo faced the Covid 19 pandemic, almost like any other country in the world, in 2020. Yet, the government, both the legislative and executive branches, has maintained the pace of legislative and regulatory activity to some extent. In this regard, environmental, energy and natural resource legislation and policy have been updated, revised or consolidated, depending on the necessity or urgency of the issues brought to the government's attention. With this in mind, we will focus in this review on the characteristic elements of international law that are of interest to us before devoting developments to aspects of municipal law.

(2) INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL LAW

By Act No. 32-2020 of 27 June 2020, the Congolese parliament granted the government an authorisation to ratify the revised treaty establishing the Economic Community of Central African States. Thus, Decree No. 2020-184 of 27 June 2020 proceeded to ratify the revised treaty of 18 December 2019 establishing the Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS).

It is important to recall that ECCAS is an organisation whose mission is to promote cooperation and strengthen regional integration in Central Africa. Its missions extend to all areas of political, economic, monetary, social and other activities.

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The revised Treaty of 2019 includes three areas of community policy that relate directly to the environment, energy and natural resources issues.

Its Chapter XI provides for a commitment to cooperation between States in the fields of agriculture, food, nutritional security, animal and fishery resources. In this respect, Article 63 of the revised Treaty stipulates that ECCAS pursues the objective of establishing an economic union through the harmonisation of national policies in the fields of industry, transport and communications, energy, agriculture, natural resources, trade, currency and finance, banking activities, human resources, humanitarian aid, environment and climate, tourism, education and culture, science and technology, etc.

In this perspective, this cooperation is based on the following objectives:

- * Raising the standard of living of rural populations, in particular by increasing incomes, through increased agricultural and fisheries production and job creation;
- * Meeting the food needs of populations and strengthening food security, in particular by improving the quantity and quality of food production and defining a policy for trade and food reserves;
- * Improving living and working conditions in rural areas;
- * Adding value locally to agricultural production through the processing of plant and animal products;
- * The development of the capacity of populations to ensure their own development, in particular through greater control of their technical and economic environment;
- * Assistance to populations affected by major disasters through warning tools and emergency food stocks.

Its objective is to identify the contours of the complex problems common to the States of the region and to obtain their commitment to harmonize agricultural policies, including the exchange of technical information on experiences and programmes underway in the States, the establishment of joint training programmes and contingency plans to manage food insecurity in the event of a crisis.

Secondly, Chapter XVI of the revised Treaty deals with cooperation on energy and water matters. Its purpose is to set a framework for the promotion of economic development and regional energy integration. With regard to energy, Article 72(1) provides that the EC-CAS Member States undertake to develop the Community's energy resources and promote renewable energy sources as part of the policy of diversification of energy sources.

To this end, the States are invited to harmonise their energy policies, establish a common energy policy covering the entire operational framework, from exploitation to distribution, initiate the creation of a forum for consultation on the various problems related to transport, supply and coverage of the subregion's energy needs, as well as develop the energy resources located on the territory of the States. As for water, Article 73 specifies that the Community water policy aims at conserving and developing water resources and supporting integrated management of the Community's water resources.

As a result, the objective pursued in this area is to harmonise national policies for the development of water resources, which will be supported by a regional water policy that the States are invited to design and implement, likely to promote the management of transboundary waters. In fact, it is important that the States develop an "adequate framework for consultation and coordination" whose purpose would be to resolve the various problems relating to the management of water resources, but also to discuss the management of shared or transboundary water resources.

Finally, Chapter XVII of the revised Treaty manages cooperation in environmental, biodiversity and natural resources issues. According to Article 74, the States engage, on the one hand, to conserve the natural environment of the Community area and to cooperate in the event of natural disasters and, on the other hand, to develop—at national and regional level—environmental policies likely to support an integrative approach to the management of forest ecosystems and biodiversity and regional economic integration while including social considerations.

Hence, States will voluntarily participate in harmonising their national policies for the management of forest resources and biodiversity, considering their international commitments stemming from

regional and international agreements, such as Agenda 2063 and the Paris Climate Agreement. Similarly, States are invited to set up mechanisms to combat erosion, deforestation, forest landscape degradation, desertification, and locust perils. However, this regional effort is only really likely to take effect if there are consultation frameworks that will make it possible to mobilise States around the resolution of the problems arising in these fields, particularly concerning the exploitation or the fight against the illicit exploitation of natural ecosystem resources. In addition, States will need to harmonise their disaster risk management and climate change adaptation plans.

The second feature relating to international law is the Letter of Intent relating to the establishment of a long-term partnership aiming at implementing the Investment Plan of the REDD+. Within the framework of the Central African Forest Initiative, Decree n° 2020-347 of 4 September 2020 implemented the Letter of Intent relating to the establishment of a long-term partnership aiming at implementing the Investment Plan of the REDD+ National Strategy.

For this reason, the decree created the management bodies for the implementation of the above-mentioned Letter of Intent (Article 1). Among the bodies set up are the inter-ministerial committee, the steering committee, the permanent secretariat and the programme/project management units. The supervision of the inter-ministerial committee, steering committee and permanent secretariat is ensured by the Prime Minister, while that of the management units by the ministries concerned.

Furthermore, the latest instruments of international law to be incorporated into the Congolese legal order regarded fuel management and the safety of radioactive waste management, as well as nuclear safety. By Act No. 48-2020 of 18 September 2020, the Congolese parliament authorised the Republic of Congo's accession to the joint convention on spent fuel management and the safety of radioactive waste management.

Similarly, Act No. 49-2020 of 18 September 2020 was adopted by the Congolese parliament to authorise the country's accession to the convention on nuclear safety.

This review is further solidified by the development of national legislation.

(3) NATIONAL LEGISLATION

(A) Agriculture and fisheries

By Act No. 5-2020 of 26 February 2020, the parliament created the National Agency for the Development of Agriculture and Livestock. The National Agency for the Development of Agriculture and Livestock (ANDAE) is a public body of an industrial and commercial nature, with legal personality and financial autonomy, which operates under the supervision of the Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock. Its purpose is to implement policies and strategies initiated and adopted by the Government in the field of agricultural and livestock development, as well as agricultural land use. Thus, ANDAE can submit to the Congolese government any action plan relating to the development of agricultural and pastoral sectors with high added value, in particular through:

- * Research, mobilisation and promotion of agro-pastoral investments and the implementation of partnerships with investors;
- * Encouraging stakeholders to form professional organisations;
- * Advisory support and technical assistance;
- * Encouraging the development of agro-pastoral products through the promotion of value chains and the establishment of sustainable production systems, in particular for the development of agricultural land, irrigation, farm equipment, packaging, processing or agro-industry, health and quality assurance, certification and marketing of products;
- * Establishment of action plans relating to the support of agriculture and livestock farming through the promotion and implementation of viable economic projects;
- * Research and development and the promotion of technologies.

The act also determines the organizational modalities of AN-

DAE, whose administration is ensured by a board of directors and management by a general management, as well as the financial resources that contribute to its operation.

In addition to the creation of ANDAE, the government had also tabled a bill for the creation of a national fisheries and aquaculture agency. Thereby, by Act n°6-2020 of 26 February 2020 the Parliament created the National Agency for the Development of Fisheries and Aquaculture (ANDPA). A public establishment of an industrial and commercial nature, ANDPA is endowed with legal personality and financial autonomy. Its activities will be carried out under the supervision of the Ministry in charge of Fisheries and Aquaculture.

The purpose of ANDPA is to implement policies and strategies initiated and adopted by the Government with regard to the sustainable development of fisheries and aquaculture, the preservation of fishery resources and their biotope, as well as the management of water bodies and other land or basins used for aquaculture (article 4).

ANDPA is expected to submit proposals to the Government on plans for the development of fisheries and aquaculture production systems, programmes and projects for the development of sustainable and environmentally friendly fisheries and aquaculture. To this end, ANDPA will be able to offer assistance through government activities as follows:

- * Advisory support and technical assistance;
- * The systematic and regular evaluation of fishery resources;
- * Knowledge and evaluation of other marine and continental biological resources;
- * The control of aquatic species likely to be farmed;
- * Encouraging stakeholders to form professional or inter-professional organisations;
- * Research, mobilisation and promotion of investments in fisheries and aquaculture and the implementation of partnerships with investors;
- * Encouraging the development of fishery products through the promotion of value chains and the implementation of sustainable exploitation or production systems, particularly

in terms of farm equipment, packaging, processing or industrialisation, health and quality assurance, certification and marketing of products;

* The establishment of action plans to prevent overfishing or overexploitation of fisheries resources;

* Research and development and the promotion of technologies.

In addition, the organisational arrangements for ANDAE, whose administration is carried out by a Board of Directors and management by a General Management, as well as the financial resources that contribute to its operation derive from Act n°6-2020 of 26 February 2020.

(B) Land ownership

Act No. 52-2020 of 29 September 2020 established a National Land Registry in Republic of Congo. The registry represents the documentation drawn up by the state for the identification and physical determination of built and non-built land ownership, as well as the publication of real property rights. This documentation constitutes a representative, descriptive and evaluative statement of built and non-built property, but not of property titles. The public administration plays here the crucial role of land registry, but also of a trusted third party in the procedures of real estate transactions.

The main and secondary documents of the national land register, which consist of graphic documents or plans and literal documents, include the following:

Graphic documents are as follows:

- * The cadastral map;
- * The section plan;
- * The plot map;
- * The boundary plan;
- * The parcelling out plan;
- * The land consolidation plan;

- * The updating plan;
- * The delineation plan;
- * The location plan.

Main literal documents are as follows:

- * The cadastral matrix;
- * The section status or descriptive register;
- * The land register or the national register of land ownership the demarcation report;
- * The division report;
- * The land consolidation report;
- * The updating report.

A secondary graphic document of the national land register is a secondary graphic document of the national land register:

- * The location sheet.

The following are literal secondary documents:

- * The land management control booklet;
- * The plot survey form;
- * The initial geo-referencing certificate;
- * The traceability parcel survey report;
- * The customary land recognition report.

Parliament grants the discretion to the government to create further any secondary documents by decree in the Council of Ministers.

(C) Energy resources

With a view to strengthening the conditions for the application of Article 21 of the Congolese Electricity Code, Ministerial Order No. 673 of 22 January 2020 set out the terms and conditions for issuing and renewing the licence to import or export electricity. Pursuant

to Article 2, the granting of a licence to import or export electricity to the Republic of Congo lies with the Minister in charge of electricity. Electricity import or export activities are part of the national energy policy. They are carried out insofar as they take into account national energy needs, trade-related regulations and the Republic of Congo's commitments to the Central African power pool.

In addition, the ministerial order determines the terms and conditions for the issuance and renewal of the licence, while specifying the composition of the licence application file, the processing fees, the procedure for the issuance and renewal of the licence, the tax regime and the conditions under which access to the public electricity transmission network is ensured. Also, the order lays out the various obligations' incumbent upon the holder of an electricity import or export licence.

Pursuant to Article 8 of Decree no. 2017-254 of 17 July 2017, Decree no. 2020-132 of 18 May 2020 set the consumption bands for the volumes of water applicable to the various categories of users of the public water service. The consumption brackets are established on the basis of the volumes of water consumed by social categories such as households and individuals. The decree allocates the users of the public water service according to whether households/private individuals belong to category I; public administrations to category II; large consumers to category III; and industrial and tourist consumers to category IV (Article 3).

Article 3 of Decree No. 2017-252 of 17 July 2017 provides that the energy consumption bands will be set by a subsequent regulation. In this respect, Decree no. 2020-133 of 18 May 2020 therefore determines the energy consumption brackets applicable to the various categories of users of the public electricity service. However, the consumption brackets are set in relation to the power subscribed to by users and in line with the ceiling for social brackets set out in Article 3 of the decree. These include households/private individuals in category I; Low Voltage professionals in category II; Medium Voltage professionals in category III; and High Voltage professionals in category IV.

Additionally, in order to resolve procurement problems under Act No. 14-2003 of 10 April 2003 on the Electricity Code, Decree No. 2020-145 of 5 June 2020 set up an interministerial committee

responsible for assisting the Government in the choice of delegated managers of public electricity production, transmission and distribution facilities. The committee—which exercises its mandate under the authority of the Prime Minister—is the body responsible for awarding contracts and evaluating bids. It is composed of a procurement commission and a sub-commission for the analysis of bids. The mission of the procurement commission is to approve the results of the analysis and evaluation of applications, bids or proposals, while the task of the sub-commission for the analysis of bids is to scrupulously analyse applications, bids or proposals and their ranking.

(D) Natural resources

Natural resources are at the heart of the national industrialisation policy adopted through Decree No. 2020-32 of 26 February 2020. This policy, namely the national industrialisation strategy, outline the main orientations for the industrialisation of Congo.

The country's development is based on this strategy, which pursues the objective of irreversible diversification the national economy; the acceleration of economic growth; the creation of a large number of jobs making it possible to combat mass unemployment; a better supply of the domestic market and consequently a control of the general evolution of prices and the improvement of foreign trade. As a result of this strategy, the Republic of Congo will—inter alia—proceed with industrialisation through the development of natural resources. The annex to the decree underlines the major role that the policy gives to the natural resources sector as follows:

(...) Industrialisation through the valorisation of natural resources essentially aims to promote exports. It is a question of doing everything possible to ensure that the resources that abound in our soil (22 million hectares of dense forests of which 18.4 million hectares can be exploited in wood species) and subsoil (60 billion tonnes of limestone, 25 billion tonnes of proven iron reserves, 1.8 billion tonnes of proven potash reserves, 34 billion cubic metres of proven gas reserves, 7.6 billion tonnes of proven and estimated

oil reserves, etc.) are valorised by industries, with a view to satisfying mainly external demand. (Chapter II, para. 2).

In furtherance of consolidating the institutional bodies that contribute to transparency in the management of natural resources, Ministerial Order No. 5381 of 19 March 2020 laid rules organising the permanent secretariat of the National Council for the Implementation of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative. The decree sustained Decree n° 2019-383 of 27 December 2019 on the creation, attributions, organisation and functioning of the National Committee for the implementation of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative as well as Decree n° 2019-394 of 28 December 2019 on the appointment of the permanent secretary of the National Committee for the implementation of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative.

The permanent secretariat of the national EITI committee—which it sets up—will carry out its mission under the supervision and oversight of the permanent secretary. The permanent secretariat includes an operational technical unit and an administrative management unit that will ensure its management and operation.

In accordance with Act n°16-2000 of 20 November 2000 on the forestry code, Ministerial Order n° 6515 of 18 June 2020 defining the standards for reduced impact logging in the Republic of Congo is issued. This order prescribes the standards for reduced impact logging in the Republic of Congo. This is the national reference framework for the development of management plans for production series and annual exploitation plans, which enables these policies to be integrated into an overall context of sustainable management of forest resources (article 2). Reduced impact logging should be referred to as “a set of logging operations planned and monitored continuously, in order to reduce the impact on the forest stand and the environment.”

With regard to the general standards for reduced impact logging, it should be noted that logging activities that have an impact on the forest stand and the environment consist of:

- * Exploitation inventory and mapping of the resource;
- * The opening up of the road network;

- * Felling and topping;
- * Skidding and skidding;
- * Timber processing and handling operations in the forest.

Similarly, the government will be able to add to this list other activities that will appear in the management plans for production series and annual exploitation plans.

Exploitation inventory standards are provided for in Decree No. 2002-437 of 31 December 2002 and the operation is carried out on the basis of systematic counting. These standards take into account the need to set up signage and materialisation of the boundaries of the forest production unit and of the annual logging base in preparation, the delimitation of counting plots, the diameter and quality of the barrels, the marking with paint of the species marketed by the company, as well as the topography of the environment, the presence of tracks and campsites. As for the mapping of resources, this is drawn up annually on a scale of 1/20,000 and specifies the trees of the species to be developed and protected, such as future trees, heritage trees, centenary trees or natural museums, seed trees and prohibited species.

Subsequently, the thematic maps drawn up present the extent of available forest resources, while indicating the constraints on the ground, such as sensitive areas. In addition, a reduced impact forestry evaluation grid is also provided in order to simplify the implementation or adjustment of action plans by forestry sector stakeholders. This grid allows an audit to be carried out using 72 verifiers, who cover forest exploitation activities, the promotion of local development, working conditions and wildlife management.